

Figure 2. Activity of mouse DRGs cultured in MFCs, non-compartmentalized and co-cultured with human keratinocytes. (a)–(c) Calcium imaging recordings of DRGs cultured in MFC. (a) Representative fluorescent signals recorded in the soma of Did^+ neurons stimulated in the axonal compartment. Y-axis represents fluorescence normalized with respect to that evoked by KCl in the soma compartment (KCl). (b) Percentage of response of Did^+ neurons normalized with respect to the response evoked by KCl^+ in the soma. (c) Size of the response normalized with respect to the response evoked by KCl^+ in the soma. Data are as mean \pm SEM, every dot is a cell. $N = 4$ animals, two males and two females; $n \geq 2$ coverslips per animal; total number of crossing neurons=747. (d)–(f) Calcium imaging measurements of non-compartmentalized DRGs. (d) Representative fluorescent signals of responsive neurons. Y-axis represents fluorescence normalized to that evoked by KCl. (e) Percentage of responses. (f) Size of the response normalized to KCl. Data are mean \pm SEM. $N = 4$ mice, two males and two females. $n \geq 2$ coverslips per animal. Total number of neurons= 5498. (g)–(i) Scanning electron microscope pictures of the axonal compartment of co-cultured DRGs with human keratinocytes. The dashed line indicates the end of the microchannels. The white square indicates high magnification views of the selected area. Scale bars: 100 μ m (g), 10 μ m and 500 nm (h), and 10 and 2 μ m (i). (j)–(l) Calcium imaging measurements of co-cultured DRGs with keratinocytes. (j) Representative fluorescent signals of responsive neurons. (k) Percentage of response of Did^+ neurons normalized with respect to the response evoked by KCl^+ in the soma. Mean \pm SEM. (l) Size of the response normalized with respect to the response evoked by KCl^+ in the soma. Data are mean \pm SEM, every dot is a cell. DRGs-keratinocytes co-culture: $N = 4$ animals, two males and two females; $n = 2$ coverslips per animal; total number of crossing neurons = 298.